

JOBS IN THE MERCHANT NAVY: AN OVERVIEW OF ESSENTIAL QUALIFICATIONS REQUIRED

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Introduction

There is a saying that 'if the ships of the world stopped, half the world would freeze and the other half would starve', and it is literally true. Even today, 95 percent of the world's goods are transported by sea. It includes essential commodities like food grains, fertilizers, crude oil, fuels, chemicals, and gas. Currently, there are more than 50,000 large ships in the world. India plays an important role in providing the manpower required to operate these ships. It includes captains, shipping officers, marine engineers, and other personnel.

The Indian Ocean Coast is a great gift for our country. Waterways are very important in the supply chain. 95 percent of global logistics and 70 percent of cargo are carried by ships. We still have low awareness about jobs in the shipping sector. Indeed, it is not an exaggeration to state that the shipping industry has provided numerous job prospects. Under the 'Sagarmala Scheme' of the Central Government, many training institutes have taken up the task of imparting training in logistics management, navigation, and inspection.

Calling NARI SHAKTI

Although there has been an increase in the number of women employees in the maritime industry over the past few years, the number of women employees are far less than the global average. Most of them are working as chief officers or sailors, and some of them take part in sailing on a large scale. The largely male-dominated maritime sector is expected to see an increase in the number of female employees in the coming years, thanks to increased awareness. Women professionals can get better job roles as maritime companies come up with new policies.

Passion to Profession

Students aspiring to join the Merchant Navy must have a strong mindset, as it is a somewhat offbeat career. It is different from the white-collar jobs of 'nine to five'. It involves being away from home for several months (currently four to six) and facing extreme conditions like heat and rain, storms and wind, snow, and bitter cold. Communication, team-work, proficiency to perform given task, and right aptitude are some of the important skills required to survive in this field.

The officer has to work day and night, anytime, and sometimes for several hours in a row. Still, the career is popular among adventurous youth, and nowadays some young women are also attracted to this field. Reasons for this attraction include opportunities for world travel, a good salary (often in tax-free foreign currency), long (2-3 months) consecutive vacations, and early financial self-reliance for the executive class.

Formal Education

Indian Maritime University is instrumental in imparting formal education through various job oriented courses and program leading to recognised degrees and diplomas.

After completing formal education and mandatory certifications, students can get good job opportunities in the maritime industry. Apart from this, the Central Government has radically revised the curriculum as per the new National Education Policy 2020. The aim is to create skilled manpower through research, quality education, and partnerships with industry.

About Indian Maritime University

The IMU was established in 2008 by an Act of Parliament and is under the administrative control of the Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways. The IMU's vision is to be a world-class university that fosters excellence in maritime education and research. The Indian Maritime University (IMU) is a central university that offers education and research in the field of maritime studies. The IMU has six campuses across India, located in Chennai, Mumbai, Kolkata, Visakhapatnam, Cochin and Andaman & Nicobar Islands. The IMU offers undergraduate, postgraduate and doctoral programs in various disciplines such as nautical science, marine engineering, naval architecture, ocean engineering, maritime law, maritime management and logistics. The IMU also conducts examinations and awards certificates for seafarers and maritime professionals.

Academics

IMU has four schools that offer various programmes in maritime disciplines. The schools are: School of Marine Engineering & Technology, School of Naval Architecture and Ocean Engineering, School of Nautical Science and School of Maritime Management. IMU also has academic regulations, calendars, journals, magazines and guidelines for affiliation.

Admissions

IMU conducts a common entrance test (CET) for admission to its programmes. Candidates can apply online through the IMU website and pay the application fee. The admission process also involves counselling, document verification and medical examination.

Eligibility Criteria

The eligibility criteria for various Merchant Navy courses offered by the Indian Maritime University and other leading institutes in India are designed to ensure that candidates have the necessary knowledge, skills, and physical fitness to excel in this challenging and rewarding profession. Aspiring students are advised to visit official website of IMU <https://www.imu.edu.in/> to know more about eligibility criteria of various courses and admission related information.

Some of the Job Roles

Deck Department

Captain/Master - The highest-ranking officer responsible for overall ship operations.

Chief Officer - Assists the captain and oversees the deck crew.

Second Officer and Third Officer - Involved in navigation, safety, and cargo operations.

Engine Department

Chief Engineer - in charge of the ship's engine room and overall mechanical operations.

Second Engineer and Third Engineer - Assist the chief engineer in maintaining and operating the engine systems.

Electro-Technical Department

Electro-Technical Officer (ETO) - Handles the ship's electrical and electronic systems.

Career Path

Navigating Officers

(these may rise to the rank of Captain),

Marine Engineers

(who later become Chief Engineer), and

Electro-Technical Officers

Conclusion

Job opportunities can vary based on the type of vessel (container ships, tankers, bulk carriers, etc.) and the specific needs of shipping companies. The merchant navy provides a global career, allowing individuals to travel and work in diverse environments. It's important to stay updated on industry requirements and regulations for career progression.

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